

Keep going!

Your publication has been reviewed and will be published soon.

→ Move forward 2 spaces

Creative Commons Licence

You published your work with a licence supporting open access principles.

Well done!

→ You receive
1 reputation point

Peer Review

You volunteered to conduct peer reviews for scientific papers.

This enhances your visibility and reputation. (Unfortunately, there is no monetary compensation 😞)

→ You receive
1 reputation point

Green, green, green are all my publications

You published your paper via green open access.

→ You receive 1 reputation point and may roll the dice one more time!

Let it show!

Your research profiles are up to date and well maintained.

Your accomplishments are visible to everyone.

→ You receive
2 reputation points

All that glitters is gold

You published your paper via gold open access in a prestigious journal.

→ You have to pay 2 coins,
but you get 3 reputation
points!
And you get to roll the
dice again!

Let's talk about ...

The conference fits your research field, but to attend it a participation fee is required.

→ You have to pay 1 coin!

Paywall Alarm!

The paper fits your research question and withholds valuable information. Unfortunately, an access fee is required.

→ You have to pay 1 coin!

Oh, no! Licence missing.

You did not apply for a Creative Commons license for your work. As a result, the publisher now holds the copyright.

→ Advance to the Copyright Trap and lose one turn.

APC Shock!

Your preferred journal requires very high publication fees (Article Processing Charge).

→ You have to pay 2 coins!

Beware of predators!

You fall for a predatory publisher. This does not only cost the publication fee but also reputation points.

→ You must surrender 3 reputation points and 2 coins!

Inbox full!

You receive questionable emails from fake journals offering to publish your paper. You lose valuable time and time is money.

→ You have to pay 1 coin!

Funding requirement not fulfilled!

In contrast with the funding requirements you did not publish open access. How rude!

Besides, Closed Access is less visible.

→ You must give up
2 reputation points or
sit out 1 round!

Surviving Peer Review!

One reviewer made many remarks on your work and pointed out several mistakes. You will need some time to make the corrections.

Nevertheless, the quality of your scientific output increases.

→ You must skip 1 round
and receive
1 reputation point!

Embargo Catch-22!

Your work has been published in a prestigious journal, but there is one issue: the journal places an embargo on your paper. As a result, it will not be open access immediately.

→ You must skip 1 round
and receive
1 reputation point!

Data dilemma!

You did not publish the research data associated to your paper. That is not FAIR!

→ You must give up
1 reputation point!

Every word counts!

You received royalties for your publication.

→ You will receive 1 coin!

Diamonds are an author's friend!

You published your paper via diamond open access.

→ You receive 2 reputation points and may roll the dice one more time!

Lost in evaluation!

Research performance is under assessment at all times.

Your Bibliometrics and Reporting Team provides support to increase your impact and visibility.

→ Advance to the Bibliometrics and Reporting space.

Citations, citations, citations!

Your publication is acknowledged by the scientific community and is cited often.

→ You receive 2 reputation points

Money makes academic publishing go open ...

Publication fees are required for your paper (Article Processing Charges - APCs). Your library covers the fees. Yay!

→ Advance to the
Publication Fund space.

FAIR and fabulous!

You intend to publish your research data according to the FAIR principles. This way, your data will be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

→ Advance to the
Research Data
Management space.